

Light tuning CO/H₂ composition on Ag: Unraveling CO₂ mass transfer and electron-phonon coupling in plasmon-enhanced electrocatalysis

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ABSTRACT: Plasmon-enhanced electrocatalysis (PEEC) is an emerging approach to mitigate CO₂ emissions. The mechanisms behind CO₂ adsorption and reduction at the catalyst–electrolyte interface in PEEC still need to be further explored. Herein, we employ a well-defined Ag nanostructure to elucidate these pivotal issues. By shining light with wavelengths of 625, 525, 405 nm on Ag, an adjustable CO/H₂ ratio from 35 to 1 can be obtained. The reaction pathway changing under plasmonic excitation does not originate from the lowered CO₂ mass transfer in the vicinity of Ag, as the electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance results unravel that a slightly elevated temperature in bulk electrolyte caused by light irradiation cannot weaken the CO₂ adsorption at the Ag catalyst–electrolyte interface. Theoretical calculations reveal that optical excitation towards shorter wavelengths leads to a progressive lowered energy barrier for H₂ formation together with an enhanced energy barrier for *COOH formation. Although thermodynamically suppressed, CO₂ reduction can still be improved kinetically by optimizing the excitation wavelength and intensity, being accompanied with the enhanced photocurrent. Transient absorption spectroscopy results further correlate the higher photocurrent with a prolonged electron-phonon coupling time, verifying that the improvement of CO₂ reduction kinetics in PEEC can be realized by hot electron harnessing.

KEYWORDS: plasmonic catalysis, photoelectrochemical CO₂ reduction, CO/H₂ ratio, hot electron generation, electron-phonon coupling, thermal effect

1 Introduction

Electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) is a feasible pathway to alleviate the overdependence of human society on fossil

fuels [1–7]. The mixture of CO and H₂ with a wide range of ratios is a common and valuable CO₂ reduction product [8–11], which can be further transformed into other useful chemicals and fuels [12–14]. CO/H₂ ratio ranging from 0.5 to 1.0, known as syngas [15], features a crucial industrial feedstock for the alcohol synthesis and Fischer–Tropsch reactions [16–18]. In contrast, the CO-dominant mixture is an indispensable feeding gas for C–C coupling in tandem electrocatalysis [19]. The manipulation of CO and H₂ with controllable ratio in conventional CO₂ electroreduction can

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easily be realized by modifying the morphologies and particle sizes of electrocatalysts [20, 21]. Despite that, all these pre-electrolysis optimization approaches cannot change the fact that once the structurally optimized electrocatalysts are assembled into the electrochemical cells, tuning the applied potential is the only possible way to alter the reaction pathway for the conventional electrochemistry. Plasmon enhanced electrocatalysis offers a possible way to manipulate the ongoing electrocatalytic reactions, because it is performed by shining light on the plasmonic metal electrodes concurrently with an applied voltage [22–25]. Localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) as the collective oscillation of conduction electrons in nanostructured metals [26], results in the enhanced optical subwavelength localization of electromagnetic energy [27–30], which can facilitate the activation of molecules directly [31, 32]. Furthermore, the hot carriers from the non-radiative plasmon decay can overcome the sluggish kinetics of the specific chemical reactions and further tune the reaction selectivity [33–39]. In principle, the introduction of LSPR into CO₂ electroreduction can generate the adjustable CO/H₂ mixtures.

Silver is a promising material for plasmon-enhanced CO₂ electroreduction, because of not only its robust production of CO and H₂ in electrochemical CO₂ reduction [20, 21, 40], but also its highly tunable LSPR wavelengths ranging from visible (vis) light to ultraviolet (UV) region [41]. Especially for Ag, of which electrons under intraband excitation can be pumped to the unoccupied states above the Fermi level (E_F), giving rise to the hot electrons with higher energy [42–44]. Because of the different energy barrier for triggering the H₂ formation and CO generation, changing the proportion of hot electrons is likely to facilitate one reaction and inhibit the other. Additionally, the hot electron harnessing in the plasmon-mediated process can be easily controlled by changing the excitation wavelength and intensity [45]. Consequently, on top of electric potentials, plasmonic excitation can be another variable to manipulate the CO/H₂ ratio on Ag in electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction (Fig. 1).

Despite the advantage of LSPR in manipulation of electrochemical reactions, many key issues in plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction need in-depth investigation. (I) *COOH intermediate formation is one of the rate-determining steps in electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction to CO [46]. LSPR as another energy input in addition to electric potentials, may change the *COOH intermediate formation energy to a certain extent. The non-radiative plasmon decay occurs via intraband excitation or interband transition [47]. Investigating the effect of interband transition on a plasmonic cathode in CO₂ reduction intermediate formation has been attached importance to [40]. However, uncovering the impact of intraband excitation wavelengths on the formation of *COOH intermediate in plasmon-enhanced electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction is still rarely investigated. (II) Hot electron dictates the photocurrent density in plasmonic electrocatalysis and more long-lived hot electrons can result in the current density enhancement (CE) [48]. Hence, unraveling the influence of electron-phonon (e-ph) coupling on hot electron transport is crucial to trace the origin of current density enhancement in plasmon-enhanced electrocatalysis (PEEC). Nevertheless, correlating the hot electron transport in plasmon-enhanced electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction with electron-phonon coupling has seldom been reported. (III) Furthermore, thermal effect in plasmonic catalysis cannot be neglected because of its coexistence with hot electron generation (HEG) and role in facilitating the activation of reactants [49, 50]. The hot electrons exchanging their energy with lattice phonons results in the local heating (LH) on plasmonic electrode. However, the generated heat has a limited effect on the temperature rising of aqueous solution surrounding medium in plasmonic electrocatalysis owing to the much larger specific heat capacity for aqueous solution electrolyte than that for plasmonic metals [51]. Consequently, the slightly elevated temperature in bulk electrolyte solution is probably much lower than the temperature on the surface of plasmonic electrode. How this temperature difference between plasmonic electrode and

Figure 1 The schematic illustration of how the plasmon excitation serves as an additional variable manipulates the reaction selectivity in the ongoing electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction reaction.

bulk electrolyte influences the CO₂ adsorption and mass transfer at the plasmonic electrode–electrolyte interface remains unknown. Therefore, a clear elucidation of these elusive issues is crucial for better understanding the essence of plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction.

As per the principles and motivation mentioned above, we employed Ag triangle nanoplates (Ag-TN) with a broad visible light response as the catalyst to shed light upon these elusive issues in plasmon-enhanced electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction, because the wide visible spectral response of Ag-TN is beneficial for solar energy harvesting and unraveling the wavelength-dependent photoelectrochemical performance. Considering that the electrocatalysts with complicated structures or multi-components usually produce uninterpretable results in electrocatalysis [52], we accordingly minimized the complexity of the plasmonic electrocatalyst and did not alloy or couple Ag with other components.

2 Results and discussion

2.1 Structural characterization and optical properties

Ag nanocatalysts were synthesized by a wet-chemical approach [21]. The triangle nanoplate morphology of the synthesized Ag nanocrystals can be seen clearly from the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image (Fig. 2(a)) and the edge length of Ag-TN is 30 nm (Fig. S1 in the Electronic Supplementary Material (ESM)). The lateral view of Ag-TN in the TEM image reveals that its thickness is around 10 nm (Fig. S2 in the ESM). The powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of synthesized Ag-TN dropcasted on carbon paper (Fig. S3 in the ESM) shows face-centered cubic (FCC)-Bragg reflections in agreement with the diffraction standard for Ag (PDF#04-0783). The high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) image further reveals the *d*-spacing of 0.24 nm in Ag-TN, corresponding to {111} facets (Fig. S4 in the ESM). A broad peak centered at 556 nm in the UV–vis extinction spectra corresponds to the intraband excitation of Ag (Fig. 2(b)) [53]. The small extinction peak around 335 nm (3.7 eV) can be ascribed to the interband transition of Ag [42]. The

optical simulation result of Ag-TN is consistent with the experimentally measured data. When the Ag nanostructure is illuminated with the irradiance angle of 0° and 90° (Fig. 2(c)), their corresponding transmittance peaks both center at around 542 nm (Fig. 2(d)), which is close to the experimentally measured value 556 nm. The corresponding maximum $|E/E_0|^2$ (E is the local electric field, E_0 is the incident electric field) enhancement estimated for the suspended Ag-TN at 542 nm is 487 and 575 under *x* and *y*-polarized normal illumination, respectively (Figs. 2(e) and 2(f)). The broad visible light response and high electromagnetic field enhancement make Ag-TN an ideal material for solar fuels production.

2.2 Plasmon enhanced electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction

As such, we conducted the plasmon-enhanced electrochemical CO₂ reduction on Ag-TN. The relevant experiments were performed by illuminating Ag plasmonic electrode with applying the bias voltage simultaneously. To probe the influence of plasmonic excitation on the CO₂ reduction activity, the light emission diode (LED) lamps with monochromatic wavelengths of 405, 525 and 625 nm were employed as the illumination sources. The linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) results clearly show that illumination does enhance the total current density of Ag nanocrystals in CO₂ reduction reaction (Fig. 3(a)) and the current densities under the illumination of monochromatic incident light at wavelengths of 405, 525 and 625 nm are all higher than that under dark condition. Among three excitation wavelengths, monochromatic light at 525 nm endows Ag-TN with the largest current density, confirming the expectation that the excitation wavelength closer to the plasmonic resonance peak maximum generates more hot electrons. To further reveal the effect of light excitation on the product selectivity of CO₂ reduction, Ag-TN are electrolyzed by the chronoamperometry approach at different potentials. During the potential range from −0.69 to −1.02 V, the major CO₂ electroreduction products with or without illumination are CO and H₂ (Figs. 3(b) and 3(c) and Fig. S5 in the ESM). ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectra reveal that neither formate nor other products were detected in this potential range (Fig. S6 in

Figure 2 (a) TEM image of Ag triangle nanoplates; (b) UV–vis extinction graph of Ag triangle nanoplates; (c) the optical simulation model of Ag triangle nanoplate (controllable angle of irradiance θ in the *xy* plane); (d) the simulated transmittance spectra of Ag triangle nanoplates with irradiance angle θ at 0° and 90°; (e) the simulated modulus square of the field enhancement at 542 nm under *x*-polarized normal illumination; (f) the simulated modulus square of the field enhancement at 542 nm under *y*-polarized normal illumination.

Figure 3 CO₂ reduction activity: (a) linear sweep voltammetry curves of CO₂ reduction on Ag; (b) Faradaic efficiency of CO on Ag; (c) Faradaic efficiency of H₂ on Ag; (d) linear sweep voltammetry curves of CO₂ reduction on carbon paper without loading Ag; (e) CO/H₂ ratio on Ag; (f) long-term stability test on Ag at -0.86 V under 525 nm LED illumination with the intensity of 1.04 W/cm².

the ESM). Specifically, under the dark condition, Faradaic efficiency for CO (FE_{CO}) on Ag-TN goes up from -0.69 V and reaches prime at -0.86 V with the value of 90.9%. Then the FE_{CO} decreases to 74.7% at -1.02 V afterwards. On the contrary, the variation of FE_{H_2} within this potential range has an opposite tendency. FE_{H_2} bottoms out to 2.6% at -0.86 V and then goes upwards within the potential range from -0.86 to -1.02 V.

Interestingly, 625 nm excitation wavelength does not improve the FE_{CO} on Ag-TN. The related FE_{CO} under 625 nm LED illumination at -0.86 V is 81.8%, which is nearly 10% lower than the FE_{CO} under dark condition. Moreover, with the excitation wavelength blue-shifting to 525 and 405 nm, the FE_{CO} at -0.86 V further decreases to 71.5% and 67.8%, respectively. A similar phenomenon also takes place at -0.78 V, i.e., the CO Faradaic efficiency on Ag-TN declines from 76.4% under dark condition to 67.6% under 405 nm wavelength illumination, indicating that the optical excitation enhances the hydrogen evolution, but suppresses the CO generation. In the control experiments (Fig. 3(d)), carbon paper shows negligible current densities under all conditions compared to Ag-TN, verifying that the CO₂ reduction activity does originate from Ag-TN. To further compare the effect of monochromatic light and continuous wavelength (CW) illumination on the CO₂ reduction activity, we conducted the plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments under CW irradiation, which is normally used to trigger the semiconductor photocatalytic CO₂ reaction [54]. The FE_{CO} shown in Fig. S7 in the ESM is lower than that under the illumination of all monochromatic wavelengths, confirming the advantage of monochromatic light in booming the plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity. CO/H₂ ratio is a crucial indicator reflecting the reaction pathway change on Ag-TN with or without the light excitation. Within the potential range between -0.69 and -1.02 V, the CO/H₂ ratio decreases with the illumination wavelength shifting from 625 to 405 nm (Fig. 3(e)). Specifically, the CO/H₂ ratio at the potential of -0.86 V is 35 under dark condition, while 625 nm excitation light lowers this ratio to 7.1. When the excitation

wavelength blue-shifts to 525 and 405 nm, the corresponding CO/H₂ ratio further decreases to 3.7 and 3.4, respectively. Furthermore, the excitation of 405 nm monochromatic light even results in a 1:1 molar ratio of CO/H₂ at -0.94 V. Moreover, the CO/H₂ ratio and current density under light excitation only decay slightly in the 8 h long-term stability test (Fig. 3(f)), as FE_{CO} and FE_{H_2} on Ag-TN over time nearly remains unchanged (Fig. S8 in the ESM). These results verify the perfect durability of Ag-TN in plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction to produce the mixture of CO and H₂. As demonstrated above, visible light excitation successfully realizes the adjustable modulation of CO/H₂ molar ratio from 35 to 1. The mixture of CO and H₂ with extremely high CO content is a crucial feeding gas for achieving the C-C coupling in tandem electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction process [55]. On the other hand, the syngas with a 1:1 stoichiometric CO/H₂ ratio can be converted to aldehydes via the oxo synthesis and hydrocarbons by the Fischer-Tropsch process [18]. Therefore, light excitation offers the possibility to flexibly tune the CO/H₂ ratio and select the reaction pathway based on demands.

2.3 Reaction pathway and kinetics

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations can shed light upon the mechanism behind the effect of plasmonic excitation on changing the reaction pathway [56, 57]. Generally, the formation of the carbon-bound intermediate *COOH and *CO desorption are the two key steps for CO₂ conversion to CO [46]. Since *CO can desorb readily on Ag surface [8, 46], the rate-determining step in our system can be simplified as *COOH formation [58]. To compare *COOH formation energy difference between dark conditions and light illumination, the transition state (TS) was introduced into the calculations to show the energy barrier changes under different excited states and ground state (GS). In plasmon-mediated process, hot electrons usually undergo a rapid energy decay. However, the time-dependent DFT calculations results unveiled that CO₂ can trap hot electron at the timescale of 100 fs [59], which is shorter than the carrier relaxation time in plasmonic

nanostructures [60]. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that TS can retain its state in the plasmonic excitation process. Moreover, to keep DFT calculations consistent with the real experimental conditions, we used an implicit solvation model in the calculations, i.e., CO_2 reacts with H_2O instead of proton. Therefore, the calculation of the overall energy barrier is considered to be in a solvent environment. As the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) competes with CO_2 reduction simultaneously, the energy barrier of H_2 generation with and without light excitation is also investigated. Furthermore, combining transition state and implicit solvation model to investigate the $\text{CO}_2\text{RR}/\text{HER}$ reaction barrier in electrocatalytic processes has been successfully proposed [61], making our calculation model and method more convincing. To elucidate the impact of the plasmonic excitation on the reaction pathway, we utilized excitation energies approximately matching the corresponding incident light wavelength to show the energy difference between ground state and excited state [56, 57]. Based on the sketch shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), we successfully obtain the energy barriers for the formation of $^*\text{COOH}$ and H_2 at ground state and excited state (Figs. 4(c) and 4(d)) using climbing image nudged elastic-band (CINEB) [62] and the delta self-consistent field (SCF) approaches with implicit solvation model [63, 64]. In terms of $^*\text{COOH}$ intermediate formation, as shown in Fig. 4(c), its energy barrier on Ag (111) at ground state is 1.87 eV. However, 1.85 and 3.15 eV excitation energies, approximately equivalent to the energy of monochromatic light with the wavelengths of 405 and 625 nm, increases the $^*\text{COOH}$ formation energy barrier to 2.01 and 1.89 eV, respectively. In principle, the enhanced energy barrier for the $^*\text{COOH}$ formation is definitely detrimental to CO_2 activation. On the other hand, H_2 forms more easily under light excitation. H_2 formation energy barrier at the ground state is 0.75 eV, while the

light excitation with energy of 1.90 and 2.81 eV decreases the H_2 formation energy barrier to 0.67 and 0.62 eV, respectively (Fig. 4(d)). Consequently, DFT calculation results reveal that the enhanced light excitation energy weakens the $^*\text{COOH}$ formation on Ag nanostructures, but facilitates H_2 formation. *In-situ* electrochemical attenuated total reflectance-surface enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (ATR-SEIRAS) measurements (Figs. S9–S11 in the ESM) further support the DFT calculation results. The spectra measured in CO_2 saturated NaHCO_3 aqueous solution electrolyte show a broad peak between $1600\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. S10 in the ESM), which probably originates from the overlap of C=O stretching vibration and O–H bending vibration of H_2O . To rule out the interference of interfacial H_2O , the ATR-SEIRAS experiments were further accomplished in the electrolyte with D_2O as the solvent instead of H_2O (Fig. S11 in the ESM). The peak around 1668 cm^{-1} under dark condition can be ascribed to the C=O asymmetric stretching vibration of $^*\text{COOH}$ [65, 66]. This peak intensity becomes weaker under the light illumination, indicating that the $^*\text{COOH}$ formation is weakened under the plasmonic excitation. Therefore, it is evident that the promoted hydrogen evolution under the plasmonic excitation inhibits the coupling of proton and CO_2 , further suppressing $^*\text{COOH}$ formation. Electrochemical *in-situ* ATR-SEIRAS tests and DFT calculation experimentally and theoretically explain the variation of CO/H_2 ratio with and without light excitation.

Although the light excitation lowers the FE_{CO} , the hot electrons generation from the plasmon decay results in the enhancement of the total current density. Multiplying the current density by FE_{CO} , we obtained the CO partial current density with and without light excitation. As shown in Fig. S12 in the ESM, the CO partial current densities (j_{CO}) with the system under illumination are all higher

Figure 4 (a) Sketch of initial and final states of CO_2 reduction on Ag (111); (b) sketch of initial and final states of the hydrogen evolution on Ag (111); (c) $^*\text{COOH}$ formation energy barrier at GS and excited states on Ag (111); (d) H_2 formation energy barrier at GS and excited states on Ag (111); in (a) and (b), blue, red, gray and white spheres represent Ag, O, C and H atoms, respectively.

than that under dark condition and 525 nm excitation wavelength shows the highest j_{CO} . Tafel slope, as an important parameter revealing the reaction kinetics, is further employed to unveil the effect of the excitation wavelength on plasmonic electrochemical performance. Generally, a smaller Tafel slope corresponds to the lower activation energy required for promoting the electrochemical reaction. As revealed in Fig. S13 in the ESM, the Tafel slope for CO generation under dark condition is 297 mV/dec. The excitation at wavelengths of 405, 525 and 625 nm leads to the corresponding Tafel slopes for Ag-TN being 316, 282 and 320 mV/dec, respectively (Fig. S13 in the ESM). This result confirms that 525 nm excitation wavelength optimizes the CO generation kinetics.

Apparently, tuning the plasmonic excitation wavelength can manipulate the reaction pathway and kinetics. In addition to the wavelength-dependent effect, the plasmonic excitation intensity at a specific wavelength probably affect the reaction activity as well. Since 525 nm monochromatic light prevails over other illumination wavelengths in overcoming the sluggish kinetics of CO₂ reduction on Ag, the plasmonic excitation wavelength was further retained at 525 nm to correlate plasmonic excitation intensity with the electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity. With the power density increasing from 0.61 to 1.04 W/cm², the total current density enhances gradually (Fig. S14 in the ESM). In terms of the product selectivity, FE_{CO} at all potentials declines slightly, while the

hydrogen Faradaic efficiency increases (Fig. S15 in the ESM). Regarding the CO/H₂ ratio, the corresponding value at -0.86 V under the excitation intensity of 0.61, 0.83 and 1.04 W/cm² is 4.91, 4.72 and 3.72 (Fig. S16 in the ESM). These results show that the influence of excitation intensity on CO/H₂ ratio is much weaker than that of excitation wavelength on CO/H₂ ratio.

2.4 Photocurrent and hot electron generation

Despite of the negative correlation between excitation intensity and FE_{CO}, enhancing plasmonic excitation intensity can still improve the current density significantly. Chopped light photocurrent measurements can directly reveal the photoexcited charge carrier generation under illumination [67–69], because the light switching on and off can clearly show the photocurrent originating from the surface plasmon decay [23]. Figures 5(a)–5(e) display the photocurrent density enhancements as a function of excitation intensity at 525 nm illumination wavelength at all the potentials. It is apparent that larger illumination power density results in higher photocurrent density. To verify the enhanced photoelectrochemical response originating from the hot electron generation, we extracted the photocurrent density and the illumination power density from Figs. 5(a)–5(e) and further plotted them in Fig. 5(f). In principle, the linear relation between photocurrent density and excitation intensity can confirm that the current density enhancement mainly

Figure 5 Photocurrent response on Ag-TN with the illumination of a 525 nm LED under different intensities: the chopped light photocurrent density at (a) $-0.69 V_{\text{RHE}}$, (b) $-0.78 V_{\text{RHE}}$, (c) $-0.86 V_{\text{RHE}}$, (d) $-0.94 V_{\text{RHE}}$, and (e) $-1.02 V_{\text{RHE}}$; (f) the relationship between photocurrent density and illumination power density at different potentials; the photocurrent densities caused by local heating and hot electron generation extracted from the total photocurrent densities under the illumination of a 525 nm LED with different excitation intensities: (g) 0.61 W/cm²; (h) 0.83 W/cm²; and (i) 1.04 W/cm².

arises from the hot electron generation [23]. The quasi-linear relationship between power density and photocurrent at all the applied potentials can be seen clearly in Fig. 5(f), validating that the photocurrent mainly originates from the HEG rather than LH. In addition, this linear relation between photocurrent and excitation power density also occurs at lower illumination intensities (Fig. S17 in the ESM). Chopped light photocurrent measurements with shorter time intervals directly unravel that the instant responsive time of photocurrent under light illumination is 0.07 s (Fig. S17(a) in the ESM), which is consistent with the reported data and undoubtedly confirms the existence of hot electrons [70]. A more specific way was proposed to quantify the hot electron generation (non-thermal effect) and local heating (thermal effect) from the chopped light photocurrent measurements, in which the rapid responsive photocurrent and the slow responsive photocurrent subsequent to the rapid photocurrent were ascribed to hot electron generation and local heating, respectively [70, 71]. To specifically quantify the proportion of non-thermal effect and thermal effect in our system, the rapid responsive (j_{nr}) and slow responsive photocurrent density (j_{sr}) are highlighted in Fig. 5(a) and then extracted from the total photocurrent density (j_{total}) shown in Figs. 5(a)–5(f). As clearly displayed in Figs. 5(g)–5(i), j_{nr} dominates over j_{sr} under different excitation intensities at all the potentials. In Fig. 5(i), the non-thermal effect even accounts for over 90% of total photocurrent within the potential range from -0.69 to -0.94 V and still retains over 80% of total photocurrent at -1.02 V. Non-thermal effect overwhelming thermal effect at low and high overpotentials verifies that hot electrons generation is the major reason resulting in

the photocurrent enhancement of Ag-TN in CO_2 reduction. The similar conclusion can be drawn from the wavelength-dependent chopped light results (Fig. S18 in the ESM). CE, as an important metrics evaluating the effect of plasmonic excitation on the photoelectrochemical response, can be expressed by dividing the total photocurrent density by the dark current density [72]. Figure S19 in the ESM shows that the CE scales with the power density increasing from 0.61 to 1.04 W/cm^2 , further proving the crucial role of higher plasmonic excitation rates in plasmon-assisted electrochemistry. Since the larger photocurrent density under higher illumination intensity resulted from more hot electrons generation, we further used the degenerate pump-probe technique (schematized in Fig. 6(a)) to probe the hot electron dynamics in this plasmon-mediated energy conversion processes.

2.5 Electron-phonon coupling and hot electron transport

The e-ph coupling reflects how the hot electron distribution equilibrates with lattice and longer e-ph coupling time (τ_{e-ph}) normally results in more long-lived hot electrons [45, 73]. At a fixed pump fluence of 3000 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ on the investigated Ag-TN, observed decay times in the transient absorption curves depend on the pump wavelength: The longest one (2.13 ps) is observed at a wavelength of 525 nm (Fig. 6(b)), while illuminating with 405 and 625 nm shows shorter decay times (1.88 and 1.56 ps, respectively). This indicates that the excitation at 525 nm corresponds to the longest e-ph coupling time and gives rise to the slowest hot electron annihilation. Moreover, decreasing the pump fluence at a fixed wavelength results in the faster decay of the $\Delta T/T$ (ΔT is the transmissivity

Figure 6 (a) Schematic of the degenerate pump-probe transient absorption setup (Δt is the time delay between pump and probe pulses); (b) normalized pump-probe traces at different pump wavelengths with the same pump fluence (3000 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$); (c) normalized $\Delta T/T$ pump-probe traces under excitation of 525 nm pump wavelength with different pump fluences; (d) extracted e-ph coupling times under illumination of 525 nm pump wavelength with different pump fluences.

change and T is the transmissivity) traces (Fig. 6(c)). Specifically, when the pump fluence is reduced from 3000 to 500 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ at 525 nm excitation, the corresponding e-ph coupling time decreases from 2.13 to 0.44 ps. The positive correlation between pump fluence and e-ph coupling time (Fig. 6(d)) can validate that the higher photocurrent density in plasmon enhanced electrocatalysis does originate from the longer e-ph coupling time. Undoubtedly, a longer e-ph coupling time can further improve the hot electron transport [74] at the interface between electrolyte and Ag-TN catalyst, resulting in the smaller radius impedance arc under the higher illumination intensity (Fig. S20 in the ESM). The improved interfacial electron transport caused by longer e-ph coupling time may promote the incident light-to-current conversion, which can be evaluated by the incident photon-to-current efficiency (IPCE). Coinciding with our deduction, the IPCE values at 525 nm excitation wavelength under all the potentials show the similar tendency to other experimental results mentioned above, i.e., higher illumination intensity leads to the larger photon-to-electron conversion efficiency (Fig. S21 in the ESM).

2.6 Thermal effect on CO₂ adsorption

After the electron-phonon relaxation process, the energy carried by hot electrons is released to lattice phonons of plasmonic nanostructures. Phonon-phonon coupling in plasmonic catalysts results in the local heating, which also plays a crucial role in the plasmon-mediated energy conversion processes [75–80]. The generated heat can further propagate from plasmonic nanoparticles to the surrounding medium, leading to an elevated temperature in the medium. In our plasmonic CO₂ electroreduction system, the continuously purged CO₂ gas and a fan were used to retain the reaction at room temperature. In spite of that, the temperature of electrolyte after plasmonic electrocatalytic reaction still increased by 1.0 ± 0.5 °C. Thermal imaging clearly shows temperature on working electrode under light excitation higher than that under dark condition (Fig. S22 in the ESM). Apparently, this roughly measured temperature on plasmonic electrode (T_{pe}) is higher than the temperature of bulk electrolyte (T_{be}) as well (Fig. 7(a)). The possibility may exist that higher temperature on Ag-TN over bulk electrolyte will lower the CO₂ solubility around the Ag electrode, thus further inhibiting CO₂ reduction. In this context, accurately acquiring the dynamic response at the interface between Ag electrode and CO₂ saturated aqueous electrolyte is crucial for unveiling the actual role of thermal effect in plasmonic CO₂ electroreduction reaction. Electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance (EQCM), combining both electrochemistry and quartz crystal microbalance, is a powerful tool to probe the electrode kinetics in electrocatalysis [81–83]. The mass change (Δm) on the working electrode can be correlated to the frequency shift (Δf) on the quartz crystal microbalance sensor based on the equation $\Delta f = K\Delta m$ (K refers to average sensitivity factor) [81]. Therefore, the CO₂ adsorbent mass change on the Ag-TN electrode can be easily monitored by measuring the frequency shift on quartz crystal. To investigate the impact of local heating on CO₂ adsorption in the vicinity of plasmonic electrode, we simulated the condition of the temperature on a plasmonic electrode being higher than that in bulk electrolyte. Specifically, bulk electrolyte temperature was retained at 25 °C and a peristaltic pump was used to transfer this CO₂ saturated electrolyte to the EQCM module (Figs. 7(b) and 7(c) and Fig. S23 in the ESM). The conductive QCM sensor in the EQCM module is regarded similarly as the plasmonic

electrode in CO₂ reduction and the temperature of QCM sensor can be easily controlled from room temperature to above. As the Ag-TN plasmonic electrocatalyst was dropcasted onto the QCM sensor, the temperature on it (T_{qs}) can be equivalent to T_{pe} . When Ag-TN covered QCM sensor was heated up from 25 to 32 and 39 °C (Fig. 7(d)), no dramatic difference in frequency shift took place on Ag-TN plasmonic electrode (Fig. S24 in the ESM), indicating that the adsorbed CO₂ mass on Ag-TN is not significantly affected by the higher plasmonic electrode temperatures (Fig. 7(e)). However, the situation changes with the enhancement of bulk electrolyte temperature. A significant frequency decrease on QCM sensor appear with the bulk electrolyte temperature increasing from 25 to 39 °C (Fig. 7(f) and Fig. S25 in the ESM), meaning that CO₂ adsorption mass on the Ag-TN electrode decreases remarkably (Fig. 7(g)), which is in line with the lower CO₂ solubility in bulk electrolyte in relation to the temperature enhancement (Fig. S26 in the ESM). Our EQCM results reveal that the local heating arising from the plasmon decay cannot directly weaken the CO₂ adsorption on Ag-TN electrode. The CO₂ adsorption on Ag-TN plasmonic electrode will be suppressed with the bulk electrolyte temperature rising substantially. Considering that the temperature of electrolyte almost remains unchanged after plasmonic electrocatalysis and the chemical state of Ag still retains after the light excitation (Fig. S27 in the ESM), the thermal effect does not play similar major role as the hot electrons do in our system.

3 Conclusions

In summary, utilizing Ag triangle nanoplates as a plasmonic electrocatalyst, we have successfully unraveled how the adjustable CO/H₂ ratio and current density can be achieved via altering the excitation wavelength and intensity in the plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction. DFT calculation and *in-situ* SEIRAS results unveil that blue-shift of the excitation wavelengths lowers the CO/H₂ ratio by increasing the energy barrier for *COOH formation and lowering the energy barrier for H₂ generation. In addition to the great impact of excitation wavelength on the tunable CO/H₂ ratio, photocurrent density linearly scales with excitation intensity. Pump-probe transient absorption spectroscopy result confirms that longer electron-phonon coupling time caused by higher excitation fluence results in more hot electrons being involved in the interfacial reaction, thus leading to a higher photocurrent density. By further splitting the total photocurrent density into rapid responsive photocurrent density (hot electron) and slow responsive photocurrent density (thermal effect), we identified the dominant role of hot electron in plasmonic electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction because the photocurrent resulting from hot electron accounts for more than 80% of total photocurrent density at all potentials. The limited influence of thermal effect on CO₂ adsorption on Ag-TN was further verified by electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance results. A slightly elevated temperature in bulk electrolyte initiated by local heating does not weaken CO₂ mass transfer in the close vicinity of Ag-TN. Owing to the minor contribution of local heating, the hot electron generation and harnessing is confirmed as a major impetus acquiring the adjustable CO/H₂ ratio and current density on Ag-TN. Our research successfully throws light upon CO₂ adsorption and reduction at the catalyst–electrolyte interface in plasmonic catalysis. The comprehensive characterization methods

Figure 7 (a) Schematic of thermal effect in plasmon-enhanced CO₂ electroreduction; (b) schematic of EQCM setup; (c) the illustration of EQCM module; (d) schematic of EQCM measurement under the condition of $T_{qs} \geq T_{be}$; (e) mass change on the Ag electrode under the condition of $T_{qs} \geq T_{be}$; (f) schematic of EQCM measurement under the condition of $T_{qs} = T_{be}$; (g) the mass change on the Ag electrode under the condition of $T_{qs} = T_{be}$.

used in our research will enrich the approaches for identifying the role of hot electron and thermal effect in plasmonic chemistry and provide valuable insights for the fields of solar fuels production and electrocatalysis.

4 Experimental

Chemicals. Silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99%), sodium borohydride

(NaBH₄, 99.99%), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%), sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate (ACS Reagent, ≥ 99%), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃, 99.999%), Nafion perfluorinated resin solution, isopropanol and deuterium oxide (D₂O, 99.9%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.5%) was purchased from Thermo Fischer. Sigracet 39 BB carbon paper (315 μm thickness) was purchased from FuelCellsEtc. Ultrapure water with resistivity of 18.2 MΩ·cm was obtained from Milli-Q

water purification system. CO₂ gas with purity of 99.998% was obtained from Linde.

Synthesis of Ag triangle nanoplates. 24 mL ultrapure water and 50 μ L 0.05 M AgNO₃ aqueous solution were mixed under vigorous stirring. Then the 500 μ L 0.075 M sodium citrate aqueous solution and 60 μ L hydrogen peroxide were added to the solution mentioned above successively. Afterwards, the 250 μ L 0.1 M NaBH₄ aqueous solution was added to the mixture solution and kept stirring for 30 min. The obtained dark blue suspension was rinsed by ultrapure water and centrifuged for three times. The solid product was dried in a vacuum desiccator at room temperature overnight.

Characterization. XRD of Ag triangle nanoplates was measured with a Bruker D8 advance X-ray diffractometer equipped with a Cu K α X-ray source. The sample was dropcasted onto a Sigracet 39 BB carbon paper. Data were recorded at 2θ angles between 10° and 70°. TEM measurements were carried out on JEM1011 operated at 80 kV. The TEM images of top view and side view Ag triangle nanoplates were obtained by dispersing the synthesized Ag nanostructures in isopropanol and water, respectively. HRTEM tests were accomplished on JEM-2100F operated at 200 kV. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) experiments were accomplished on the PHI quantro SXM spectrometer. UV-vis-near infrared (UV-vis-NIR) absorption data was collected on UV-vis-NIR spectrometer Lambda 750 (Perkin Elmer) with the scanning range from 300 to 1000 nm. ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance measurements were performed at 25 °C with 64 transients on an Avance III HD 500 MHz Bruker BioSpin spectrometer equipped with a broadband observe 5-mm BB-H&FD CryProbe™ Prodigy. Water suppression was performed with excitation sculpting using a pulse sequence from the Bruker pulse library (zgesgp).

Electrode fabrication. 1 mg synthesized Ag triangle nanoplates solid sample was dispersed in a mixed solution consisting of 400 μ L ultrapure water, 100 μ L isopropanol and 30 μ L Nafion solution. Then the mixture was sonicated for 15 min. Afterwards, 50 μ L suspension was drop-casted onto the confined area (0.5 cm \times 0.8 cm) on the carbon paper electrode (0.5 cm \times 2 cm). The electrode was dried at room temperature naturally.

CO₂ electrochemical reduction. CO₂RR measurement was carried out in a customized H-type cell. The electrolyte for CO₂RR measurement is 0.1 M NaHCO₃ aqueous solution, which was obtained by purging CO₂ to 0.05 M Na₂CO₃ aqueous solution overnight. The carbon paper Sigracet 39 BB loaded with Ag catalyst, a platinum mesh (2 cm²) electrode and an Ag/AgCl electrode were employed as the working electrode, counter electrode and reference electrode, respectively. Before the electrolysis, the electrolyte 0.1 M NaHCO₃(aq) was bubbled with CO₂ for 30 min. A mass flow controller (PR4000B, MKS) was used to retain the CO₂ flow rate at 30 sccm. The LSV curves and chronoamperometry data were measured under the dark condition and illumination conditions. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) experiments with and without illumination were operated at the potential of 5 mV vs. open circuit potential with frequency from 10⁵ to 0.1 Hz. All the potentials were reported with respect to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) and corrected by *iR*-drop compensation. The high-power light-emitting diode (LED) collimator sources with 22 mm clear aperture and the monochromatic wavelength at 405, 525, 625 nm (Mightex Co.) were employed as the illumination sources. An electric fan was used to cool down the H-cell during

the plasmonic electrocatalytic reaction. As a comparison, the xenon lamp (Beijing PerfectLight, MICROSOLAR300) was also used as the illumination source to shine the continuous-wavelength light (320 to 780 nm) on the plasmonic electrode. The thermal imaging tests were carried out on a forward looking infrared (FLIR) thermal imaging camera. In CO₂ reduction reaction, the generated gas products in the cathode chamber of H-cell were injected to an online gas chromatograph (Clarus 590 GC, Perkin Elmer, flame ionization detector (FID) and thermal conductivity detector (TCD)) automatically. After the electrolysis at each potential, 0.9 mL liquid product was collected and further mixed with 0.1 mL D₂O and 2 μ L DMSO for the ¹H NMR analysis. The chopped light photocurrent density measurements were accomplished on the CHI 760E potentiostat. The IPCE of Ag-TN at different potentials were calculated according to the equation: IPCE = (1240 \times j)/(λ \times P_{in}), in which j is the photocurrent density, λ represents wavelength of incident monochromatic light, P_{in} refers to the power density of the incident light.

In-situ ATR-SEIRAS measurements. In-situ ATR-SEIRAS spectra were obtained on an Fourier transform (FT)-IR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS50) equipped mercury cadmium telluride A version (MCT-A) detector. Experiments were performed at various potentials in 0.1 M NaHCO₃ using a spectroelectrochemical cell, where the Ag/AgCl electrode, Pt wire were employed as the reference electrode and counter electrode, respectively. In terms of the working electrode preparation, the catalyst ink (1 mg sample dispersed in 400 μ L ultrapure water, 100 μ L isopropanol as well as 30 μ L Nafion) was dropcasted onto the Au film covered semi-cylindrical Si prism (confined by an O-ring with Φ = 8 mm). CO₂ gas was continuously purged into the electrolyte during the reaction. Xenon lamp (Beijing PerfectLight, PLS-SXE300) equipped with band pass optical filters at wavelength of 405, 520 and 650 nm was used as the illumination source. The power densities of xenon lamp at three different monochromatic wavelengths are around 35 \pm 3 mW/cm². The spectral resolution is 4 cm⁻¹ and each single-beam spectrum was scanned on average 200 times.

EQCM test. The measurements were performed on a Q-Sense Explorer (BioLin Scientific). CO₂ gas was bubbled to 0.1 M NaHCO₃ aqueous solution at the rate of 30 mL/min. A peristaltic pump was used to transfer the CO₂ saturated NaHCO₃(aq) to the chamber of EQCM module at a rate of 50 μ L/min. Before the measurement, 30 μ L Ag-TN ink was dropcasted on the QSense Gold Sensor and dried at room temperature overnight. The electrolysis was carried out at the potentials ranging from 0 to -1.2 V vs. RHE (V_{RHE}) after the baseline of QCM frequency fluctuating less than \pm 0.5 Hz. The temperature of QSense Gold Sensor was controlled at 25, 32, 39 °C for the EQCM measurement, while the temperature of bulk electrolyte was controlled by water bath.

Pump-probe experiment. A 190 fs, mode-locked laser with an optical parametric amplifier was used to generate ultrashort pulses of tunable wavelength at 2 kHz repetition rate. The output beam was split in a pump beam, which was modulated at a frequency below 1 kHz using a chopper and a probe beam, which had a variable path length through a delay-line. They were both focused on a 1 mm thick quartz cuvette containing 10 mg/L Ag-TN colloid aqueous solution using a lens of 75 mm focal length. Since the pump beam came in at an angle and at perpendicular polarization with respect to the probe, it could be filtered out after the sample

with a polarization filter and an iris. The modulation of the probe beam transmission induced by the pump was finally detected with a silicon photodiode which was connected to a lock-in amplifier. To accurately measure the power density of the laser, the beam diameter before entering the lens was measured with the knife edge method and the peak intensity at the focus calculated with the known repetition rate, pulse length, focal length and wavelength.

Electronic Supplementary Material: Supplementary material (a description of numerical simulation approaches, DFT calculation methods, X-ray diffraction data, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis, high resolution transmission electron microscopy image, ¹H NMR spectroscopy results, Tafel slope data, excitation intensity dependent-Faradaic efficiency figures, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, wavelength-dependent chopped light photocurrent measurements and electrochemical *in-situ* ATR-SEIRAS spectra) is available in the online version of this article at <https://doi.org/10.26599/NR.2025.94907042>.

Data availability

All data needed to support the conclusions in the paper are presented in the manuscript and the Electronic Supplementary Material. Additional data related to this paper may be requested from the corresponding author upon request.

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Declaration of competing interest

All the contributing authors report no conflict of interests in this work.

Author contribution statement

R. L.: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. D. F.: Data curation, formal analysis, investigation, validation, writing – review & editing. L. M. B.: Investigation, methodology. T. P.: Investigation, methodology. Y. Z.: Investigation; J. X. Z.: Investigation. X. B. C.: Investigation. W. L.: Resources. L. A.: Investigation. A. T.: Funding acquisition, validation. L. d. S. M.: Methodology, writing – review & editing. G. M.: Resources, validation. S. H. Y.: Formal analysis, funding acquisition. S. A. M.: Resources, validation.

Use of AI statement

None.

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